

Reactivity of industrial clays subjected to mechanical activation

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Abstract. Reducing clinker content in composite cements is a key strategy to decrease CO₂ emissions in the cement industry. To increase low-grade clay substitution in cement, mechanical activation provides an alternative activation method, particularly for clays with high levels of 2:1 layer silicate minerals. However, its effects on clay reactivity are not yet fully understood fundamentally. This study evaluates mechanically activated smectite (S) and kaolinite-rich (K) clays using two tests – Strength Activity Index (SAI) and R3 test – to assess both mechanical performance and chemical reactivity in cement-based systems, using their thermally activated counterparts as reference. The clays were activated in a planetary ball mill with a ball-to-powder ratio of 10:1 and rotation speed of 500 rpm for 20 minutes; their calcined counterparts were subjected to 850 °C (K) and 750 °C (S) for 1 hour. The clays were characterized by particle size distribution, X-ray fluorescence, X-ray diffraction, and thermogravimetric analysis. The mechanical activation efficacy was analyzed as a function of mineral structure changes, heat of reaction, and strength contribution in blended cement. Results show that mechanical activation is more effective in increasing SAI for S-type clay, while thermal activation is more effective for K-type clay. The R3 test correlated well with SAI for K but did not capture the enhanced performance of mechanically activated S, likely due to the slower reaction kinetics of smectite and physical effects which affect strength development. These findings highlight the importance of combining chemical and mechanical reactivity assessments and considering clay's mineralogy when selecting activation methods.

Keywords: industrial clays; mechanical activation; reactivity; supplementary cementitious materials; thermal activation.

1 Introduction

One of the key strategies for supporting the cement industry's decarbonization efforts is reducing clinker content in composite cements. In this context, clays have stood out as Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs). While this resource is widely available, their raw form often lacks sufficient reactivity, requiring activation methods to transform their crystalline structure into a disordered and more unstable state [1].

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Thermal activation, or calcination, is a process that increases the reactivity of various clays, especially kaolinitic ones. Kaolinite is a 1:1 layered phyllosilicate mineral composed of a silicon tetrahedral sheet and an aluminum octahedral sheet in each layer [2]. The layers are linked by hydrogen bonds between hydroxyls in the octahedral sheet and oxygens in the adjacent tetrahedral sheet [3]. Calcining kaolinite at around 800°C causes its dehydroxylation, increasing the material's reactivity [4].

However, calcination appears to be less effective for clays with high levels of 2:1 layer silicate minerals, e.g. smectites [4]. In a 2:1 structure, a aluminum octahedral sheet is sandwiched in two silicon tetrahedral sheets [4]. Unlike 1:1 clays, 2:1 clays dehydroxylation does not disrupt the layers, leaving aluminum trapped between the tetrahedral sheets and limiting reactivity [5]. As a result, mechanical activation has been considered an alternative for enhancing the reactivity of such clays.

Studies have shown that mechanical activation induces structural disorder and amorphization of various minerals in clays (e.g. kaolinite, smectite, and illite) through impact and friction, enhancing their reactivity [6,7]. Some studies have demonstrated that high-energy mechanical activation can amorphize 2:1 clays when most thermal activation methods are unable to do so [4,8]. Also, mechanical activation causes particle size refinement, although specific surface area may decrease due to agglomeration [9].

Mechanical activation has been standing out in the field of clay activation given the growing interest in technologies that are not mineral-dependent [4,9,10]. However, challenges remain regarding its implementation, including the limited fundamental understanding of how it affects clay reactivity. To address this, the present study investigates mechanically activated kaolinite and smectite-rich clays using two complementary tests: the Strength Activity Index (SAI) and R3 test. The former captures the activated clay's contribution to strength development, whereas the latter isolates chemical effects in reactivity. Together, these offer a broader understanding of the effects of mechanical activation on clay performance in cement-based systems.

2 Materials and methods

This study evaluates the effect of mechanical activation on the reactivity of a smectite (S) and a kaolinite-rich (K) clay, using their thermal activated counterpart as a benchmark. SM and KM refer to mechanically activated smectite and kaolinite, while ST and KT correspond to their thermally activated counterparts. Both clays were obtained from industrial sources. Before activation, they were dried at 105 °C for 24 hours, then crushed using a jaw crusher and milled with a disc mill to reduce the particle size below 1 mm. After milling, the materials were dried again for an additional 24 hours and stored in sealed bags at room temperature (20±2°C).

Mechanical activation was carried out using a planetary ball mill (Retsch PM 100), equipped with a 125 ml zirconium oxide jar, containing zirconium oxide balls with a diameter of 20 mm. The activation process was executed in dry mode at a rotational speed set at 500 rpm, ball-to-powder (B/P) ratio at 10/1, and grinding time at 20 minutes. About 20 g of material was ground per batch (without grinding aid). After

activation, the samples were transferred into sealed containers (stored at room temperature).

Thermal activation was carried out in an electric muffle furnace. 50 ± 0.10 g of clay were placed in a quartz crucible, with an average powder depth of 1 cm. K was calcined at 850 °C and S at 750 °C for 1 hour. These calcination parameters provided the best contribution to mechanical performance for the thermally activated samples in [10] – noting that K and S samples used in this research derive from the same quarry. Calcining S at higher temperatures likely reduced 28-day strength due to phase recrystallization near the montmorillonite dehydroxylation range [11]. After calcination, the samples were cooled naturally until reaching room temperature and then stored into sealed containers. The natural cooling led to a minor water reabsorption of 0.2% for S, while no water reabsorption was observed for K.

The chemical oxide composition of the raw clays was determined via X-ray fluorescence (XRF) by the fused beads method. Both the raw and activated clays were characterized using the following methods:

- **Particle size distribution (PSD):** PSD was determined using a laser diffraction size analyzer (Malvern Mastersizer 3000), with clay samples dispersed in distilled water and subjected to one minute of ultrasonic dispersion prior to measurement.
- **X-ray diffraction (XRD):** The mineral composition was identified by XRD using an Empyrean diffractometer from PANalytical, with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda=0.154$ nm). The samples were manually ground to ensure that no more than 15% of the material was retained on the 90 μm sieve. The Profex Open-Source software was used for phase identification and quantification – with TiO_2 used as internal standard.
- **Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA):** was carried out using a Netzsch STA 449 in the temperature range of 0 to 1100°C, with a heating rate of 10°C/min under an atmosphere of 10% O_2 and 90% N_2 . Before the test, the samples were manually ground to ensure that no more than 15% of the material was retained on the 90 μm sieve. This test helped assess the clays dehydroxylation degree, calculated as the percentual difference in the weight loss between 350°C and 900°C of the activated clays and their raw reference [12].
- **Reactivity:** The clays' reactivity was assessed by the R^3 test – ASTM C1897-20 [13] – and a Strength Activity Index (SAI) [14] – based on compressive strength tests on mortars produced based on a modified version of EN196-1 [15] – previously used by [16]. Before the R^3 test, the samples were manually ground to ensure that no more than 15% of the material was retained on the 45 μm sieve.

For the modified version of EN196-1 [15], mortars were produced using a mass ratio of 1: 0.25: 3.75: 0.5 (CEM I 52,5 N, clay, sand and water). The Portland cement used contained 5% limestone addition. A reference mortar without clay replacement was prepared, together with mortars where 20% of the cement mass was replaced by activated clay. The mixtures were cast into mini prism (19×19×144 mm), compacted using a vibrating table for 2 minutes, sealed using a steel plate, and demoulded after 24 hours. Next, the specimens were submerged in a lime-saturated water bath and cured in a chamber kept at 20 °C and 90 % relative humidity until testing. Compressive strength was determined at 28 days on triplicate samples using a Universal Testing Machine, following a modified EN 196-1 [15].

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3 Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of clays

Table 1 summarizes the chemical oxide composition and loss of ignition (LOI) of the raw clays. Both clays have a $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 > 4$ and $\text{LOI} < 10$, indicating a high impurity content, e.g. quartz (SiO_2) or the presence of 2:1 minerals [17,18]. Besides, the contents of MgO and alkalis observed in S suggests the smectite nature of this clay [18].

Table 1. Elemental analysis and loss of ignition (LOI) determined by XRF for K and S.

Clays	SiO_2	Al_2O_3	Fe_2O_3	CaO	MgO	TiO_2	K_2O	Na_2O	LOI, 975°C
K	76.7	13.5	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.2	0.0	5.3
S	60.3	14.9	8.4	0.9	2.9	0.9	2.5	1.5	6.5

Fig.1 shows the diffractograms of the raw and activated clays, and the quantification of the main minerals in the raw clays. In agreement with the XRF measurements, K is a kaolinite-rich clay with a high amount of quartz. S, in turn, comprises mainly smectite.

Fig. 1. Diffractograms of raw and activated clays (including quantification of the main mineral phases in the raw clays: (a) K and (b) S.

Overall, there was a decrease in the intensity of the kaolinite peaks of K post-activation and no significant difference was found when comparing KM and KT kaolinite peaks. For the illite, the peaks signal is generally lower for KM compared to KT. Both treatments decreased the intensity of the smectite peaks in S, with slightly lower values observed for SM compared to ST. The reduction in the intensity of the peaks corresponding to the clay minerals, without their complete disappearance, indicates that there was partial amorphization of the clays [19].

The PSD and mean particle size (D_{50}) of each clay are shown in Fig. 2. For K, D_{50} increased after calcination, suggesting agglomeration occurred - a similar behavior was observed previously [20,21]. In contrast, S showed a decrease in D_{50} after thermal

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treatment. Mechanical activation reduced D_{50} in both clays. The reduction in particle size can enhance clay reactivity by promoting filler and nucleation effects.

Fig. 2. Particle size distribution of the raw and activated clays: (a) K and (b) S.

Fig. 3 shows the clays' mass loss obtained by TGA, and the dehydroxylation degree (DH) calculated as described previously. The clay K achieved almost full dehydroxylation (95.7%) after thermal treatment, whereas ST remained partially dehydroxylated (67.8%). In contrast, the mechanical treatment did not induce significant dehydroxylation for both clays. In general, the increase in reactivity caused by this activation is associated with clay amorphization rather than dehydroxylation [4].

Fig. 3. Dehydroxylation degree of the activated clays determined by TGA: (a) K and (b) S.

3.2 Reactivity assessments

Fig. 4 presents the R3 results. Both activation methods were able to increase the heat released by K and S, which indicates enhanced pozzolanic activity. For both clays, the thermally activated samples released more heat than the mechanically activated ones, indicating that calcination leads to higher reactivity.

Fig. 4. Heat released by the raw and activated clays in the R3 test after 7 days (168h):
(a) K and (b) S.

The SAI results are shown on Fig. 5. All clays, except for raw S, exhibited SAI > 80%. Both activation methods were able to increase the pozzolanic activity compared to the raw clays. For the kaolinite-rich clay, calcination led to slightly higher pozzolanic activity compared to the mechanical treatment. For smectite, mechanical activation resulted in higher pozzolanic activity compared to calcination.

Fig. 5. SAI of the raw and activated clays at 28 days.

Fig. 6 shows the relationship between the SAI at 28 days and the R3 test at 7 days for the activated clays. The heat released by the kaolinite-rich clay agrees well with SAI, both indicating higher reactivity after calcination than that of mechanical activation. The increase in pozzolanic activity after calcination can be attributed to near-complete dehydroxylation and partial amorphization observed by XRD. Although the mechanical activation was not as good as thermal activation for K according to both tests, the partial

amorphization and decrease in particle size were enough to significantly improve the clay's reactivity and provide a SAI value that is still comparable to that of KT.

Fig. 6. Relationship between SAI at 28 days and the R3 test at 7 days for the activated clays: (a) K and (b) S.

Although both tests indicate the same trend for K, a large increase in heat release in the R3 test (128%) corresponds to only a small increase in the SAI (10%), as reflected by the low slope of the curve (0.05 %/J/g) in Fig. 6a. This suggests that the increase in chemical reactivity does not translate directly into strength development. Note that SAI is also influenced by factors e.g. particle size, water demand, and packing efficiency. The larger particle size of KT compared to KM likely reduced packing density, hampering strength development. Also, differences in water demand can affect mixture consistency, further limiting mechanical performance despite the higher heat release.

For the smectite-rich clay, the heat release measured in the R3 test did not align with the SAI results. ST heat released is 35% greater than SM in the R3 test, suggesting greater chemical reactivity, yet its SAI value was ca. 20% lower than that of SM. The partial dehydroxylation of ST (67.8%), combined with its larger particle size compared to SM, was not sufficient to provide strength development comparable to SM. Nevertheless, ST's reactivity is significantly higher than its raw counterpart. The higher strength development of SM can be attributed to a combination of physical and chemical effects (i.e. partial amorphization and reduction in particle size). The lower heat release of SM versus ST can be explained by the slower reaction kinetics of the smectite compared to other clay minerals [22], indicating that the reactivity of mechanically activated smectite might not be fully captured by the R3 test timeframe.

Finally, based on SAI results, SM had the higher strength development among all clays, highlighting the potential of mechanical activation. Similar results were found in a previous study [10], where the 28-days compressive strength of mechanically activated clays were higher than the thermally activated counterparts. The reactivity assessment using the R3 test presented here complements the findings from [10], offering an approach that captures both mechanical and chemical aspects of reactivity.

In summary, while calcination is more effective for clays rich in kaolinite, the results indicate that mechanical activation shall not be excluded; this treatment enhanced both R^3 and strength development of raw kaolinite. In the case of smectite, mechanical

activation proved more effective than calcination in increasing strength. This trend was not reflected in the R^3 test, suggesting that this test may not fully capture the reactivity of mechanically activated smectite. The higher strength development observed for this clay results from a combination of chemical and physical effects.

4 Conclusions

This study analyzed the effect of mechanical activation on the reactivity of a smectite-rich and a kaolinite-rich clay. The results show that both activation methods enhance raw clay reactivity. Mechanical activation proved more effective for smectite-rich clay, mainly due to partial amorphization and particle size reduction, whereas thermal activation was more efficient for the kaolinite-rich clay, due to the effectiveness of the dehydroxylation process. For the tested clays, mechanically activated smectite had the greatest SAI, supporting the use of mechanically activated clays in composite cement.

The relationship between SAI and R^3 showed that, while both tests indicated similar trends for K, the magnitude of reactivity measured is considerably different. The 128% increase in heat release observed in the R^3 test corresponded to 10% increase in SAI. This difference highlights the influence of additional factors, (e.g. water demand and packing efficiency) on strength development that are not captured by R^3 test alone. For S, this mismatch was even more pronounced: namely, ST released 35% more heat than SM in the R^3 test, while it had ca. 20% lower SAI. The slower pozzolanic reaction kinetics of smectite, combined with physical factors affecting compactness and water demand, may limit the direct correlation between heat release and compressive strength. While R^3 is useful for evaluating chemical reactivity, it may not accurately predict strength development, particularly for clays with complex mineral structures and slower reaction rates: thus, the combination of SAI with R^3 results provides a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of activation methods on clay reactivity.

Finally, it is important to note that industrial scaling remains a challenge despite the great potential of mechanical activation in increasing clay's reactivity. To address such challenge, a fundamental understanding of the activation process for clays is needed to support in the development of more efficient grinding equipment tailored for industrial use. Additionally, knowledge on the process's energy consumption is needed to assess its overall environmental impact, let alone capital and operational costs.

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